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Corporate Monitoring Mechanisms And Tax Avoidance Of Listed Conglomerates In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The adoption of tax sheltering strategies by conglomerates in Nigeria can be attributed to several conceptual causes. Based on this, this study examined the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance of listed conglomerates in Nigeria. The study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design and utilized a panel data of sixty (60) pooled observations gathered from six (6) listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria over ten (10)-year period (2014-2023). The study also employed descriptive statistics tools and panel multiple regression technique to analyze the data with the aid of E-views 10.0 statistical package. The findings revealed that Audit committee size has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.5343{0.0165}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria, Board independence has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.62734{0.0023}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. This signifies a reduction in tax avoidance practice. CEO duality has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.4239{0.2160}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate. Institutional ownership has a non-significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.0023{0.1337}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria while Board size has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.0088{0.0102}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The Prob (F-statistics) of 0.00000 suggests that corporate monitoring mechanisms have a combined significant effect on effective tax rate (ETR) at 5% significance level. It was however concluded that corporate monitoring mechanisms play a crucial role in shaping tax sheltering strategies and other tax related activities among listed conglomerates in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that regulators and policymakers should consider implementing measures to strengthen audit committees, such as increasing their size, expertise, and independence, to enhance their ability to oversee tax compliance and reduce tax avoidance practices.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Over the years, Nigeria has witnessed rapid economic growth, attracting both domestic and foreign investors to its capital markets. As a result, the country's stock exchange has experienced considerable expansion, showcasing the presence of numerous conglomerates seeking external financing (Bassey, et al.,2024). However, this growth has also brought forth concerns related to the governance practices and tax management strategies employed by these firms. As suggested by Ismail et al. (2024), corporate governance mechanisms play significant roles in the financial operations of conglomerate firms. As such, understanding these mechanisms and strategies is crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and adherence to tax regulations. Corporate monitoring mechanisms are essential in ensuring that the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders are protected (Obidike et al., 2020). By scrutinizing the actions and decisions of management, these mechanisms aim at preventing conflicts of interest and mitigate institutional problems across listed firms in Nigeria (Paul, et al.,2025).

Effective monitoring mechanisms are especially crucial in listed companies where dispersed ownership and separation of control provide fertile ground for potential opportunistic behavior

(Emenyi., & Okpokpo, (2023). On the other hand, tax avoidance refer to legal practices undertaken by companies to minimize their tax liabilities through exploiting loopholes in tax laws or engaging in aggressive tax planning (Fagbemi et al., 2019). Emenyi et al. (2016) further argued that while tax planning is a legitimate practice aimed at optimizing tax burdens, excessive and unethical tax sheltering activities can undermine the integrity of the tax system and lead to revenue losses for governments. The variables for this study are audit committee size, board independence, chief executive officer duality, institutional ownership, board size and effective tax rate.

Given the potential interconnectedness between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance, it becomes imperative to investigate their relationship in the specific context of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Extensive research has been conducted globally on this topic. These studies include Ezejiofor and Ezenwafor (2020), Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021), Edwin and Victor (2019), Ogbeide and Osaretin (2018), Onyali and Okafor (2018), Mappadang et al. (2018). However, the Nigerian context presents unique challenges and opportunities that necessitate a comprehensive examination. In view of this, this present study draws upon existing literature and theoretical underpinnings from institutional theory and resource dependence theory to underscore the gap prevalent in the literature. By shedding light on the relationships between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance, this research study aims to contribute to the extant literature on corporate governance and taxation in Nigeria as well as provide insights that can assist policymakers, regulators, investors, and other stakeholders in formulating effective strategies for promoting good governance and curbing tax evasion in listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Tax avoidance by listed conglomerates in Nigeria poses a significant challenge to the country's revenue generation and economic development. Despite the importance of tax revenues for funding public services and infrastructure, conglomerate firms may exploit loopholes and weaknesses in tax regulations to minimize their tax liabilities. The corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance employed by listed conglomerate in Nigeria pose significant challenges in terms of accountability, transparency, and ethical tax practices. This research aims to comprehensively examine these practices within the context of Institutional theory to shed light on the conceptual causes, negative aspects, and potential gaps in the existing literature. The adoption of tax avoidance by conglomerate firms in Nigeria can be attributed to several conceptual causes. The pressure to conform to prevailing norms and expectations within the institutional environment, which influences firms to mimic the tax practices of successful peers (Udomah, & Emenyi,(2023). Also, regulative pressures stemming from formal rules and regulations imposed by the government and tax authorities can shape firms' tax management decisions. Hence the need for this present study.

There is a growing body of literature on corporate governance and tax management practices. These include studies by Ezejiofor and Ezenwafor (2020), Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021), Edwin and Victor (2019), Ogbeide and Osaretin (2018), Onyali and Okafor (2018), Mappadang et al, (2018), Uniamikogbo et al, (2019), Oyenike et al, (2016) in Nigeria; Hoseini, Gerayli et al, (2018) in Iran; Chytis et al, (2020) in Greece using several databases; among several others. These studies provide counterintuitive predictions on the link between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance. While some document a positive effect, others report a negative association. These inconsistencies could be attributed to the adoption of different surrogates, research techniques, study area and tools by previous researchers.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance of listed conglomerates in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives were to:

1. To ascertain the relationship between audit committee size and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.
2. To establish the relationship between board independence and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.
3. To investigate the relationship between chief executive officer (CEO) duality and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

4. To determine the relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.
5. To analyse the relationship between board size and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual framework

2.1.1 Corporate monitoring mechanisms

Corporate monitoring mechanisms refer to the various mechanisms and practices that are put in place to ensure effective oversight, control, and accountability within a company. These mechanisms are designed to monitor and guide the actions of corporate executives and directors, thereby promoting transparency, ethical behavior, and shareholder value. One important aspect of corporate monitoring mechanisms is the role played by the board of directors. According to Ogbeide and Osaretin (2018), the board of directors acts as the main monitoring mechanism in a company and is responsible for overseeing and guiding management activities on behalf of shareholders. The board is often composed of independent directors who are not affiliated with the company's management, and their primary role is to represent shareholders' interests and provide objective oversight. Another key monitoring mechanism is the audit committee. The audit committee is a subcommittee of the board of directors, and its primary function is to ensure the integrity of financial reporting and internal control systems. It is responsible for appointing and overseeing the external auditor, reviewing financial statements, and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards (Chytis et al., 2020).

However, other monitoring mechanisms include executive compensation and incentives, internal control systems, external auditors, and regulatory authorities (Zalata & Roberts, 2016). Through the active involvement of independent directors, audit committees, and other mechanisms, these monitoring practices help mitigate agency conflicts, promote transparency, and foster long-term value creation for all stakeholders. These mechanisms collectively aim to align the interests of executives with those of shareholders, minimize agency conflicts, and ensure that the company operates in accordance with legal and ethical standards. Ogbeide and Osaretin (2018) however noted that the effectiveness of corporate monitoring mechanisms can vary across firms and industries. Hence, corporate monitoring mechanisms play a critical role in ensuring that companies operate in the best interests of their shareholders.

2.1.2 Audit committee size

The size of the audit committee is a crucial aspect of corporate governance that can influence the effectiveness of oversight and control mechanisms within a company. In the context of tax avoidance, the size of the audit committee can have implications for the level of scrutiny and oversight of tax-related activities. Empirical studies have examined the relationship between audit committee size and tax avoidance in various countries. For instance, Agbebi et al, (2016) conducted a study on listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria and found that larger audit committees were associated with a lower likelihood of engaging in tax avoidance. This suggests that a larger audit committee size may enhance the oversight and control over tax-related activities, thereby reducing the propensity to engage in aggressive tax planning practices.

The presence of a larger audit committee can contribute to more effective monitoring and decision-making. A larger committee is likely to have a diverse range of skills, knowledge, and expertise, which can facilitate a more comprehensive and critical review of tax-related issues (Agbebi et al., 2016). This can lead to increased accountability and transparency in relation to tax planning activities, as well as a more cautious approach towards engaging in aggressive tax avoidance or evasion. Furthermore, a larger audit committee might also provide better representation and protection of shareholder interests. It can act as a check and balance mechanism against management's potential opportunistic behavior and conflicts of interest in relation to tax planning strategies (Odukoya et al., 2015). However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of audit committee size in mitigating tax avoidance is contingent upon other factors, such as the independence and expertise of committee members, their commitment to fulfilling their oversight responsibilities, and the organizational culture that encourages ethical behavior (Agbebi et al., 2016).

2.1.3 Board independence

Board independence refers to the composition of a corporate board that is free from any conflicts of interest and external influences. It ensures that board members can make decisions objectively and in the best interests of the company and its stakeholders. In the context of tax avoidance, board independence can have implications for the effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Research on the relationship between board independence and tax avoidance is limited, particularly in the Nigerian context. However, studies conducted in other countries provide insights into this relationship. For example, Hoseini et al. (2018) and Timothy et al. (2020) found that firms with more independent boards tend to have lower effective tax rates. This implies that board independence may reduce the inclination towards aggressive tax planning and tax avoidance. The presence of independent directors on a board can enhance the effectiveness of corporate oversight, including tax-related decision-making. Independent directors bring objectivity and a diversity of perspectives to discussions concerning tax planning and compliance. They are less likely to have personal or business interests that could compromise their ability to make independent judgments (Ogbodo & Abusomwan, 2021). This can help ensure that tax strategies are aligned with ethical and legal principles, rather than solely focused on minimizing tax liabilities.

Furthermore, independent directors can play a crucial role in monitoring and challenging management's tax practices. They can scrutinize the effectiveness of tax planning strategies, assess the associated risks, and hold management accountable for their decisions (Uniamikogbo et al., 2019). This active monitoring can contribute to more responsible tax practices, reducing the likelihood of excessive tax sheltering or aggressive tax planning. However, it is important to note that board independence alone may not be sufficient to ensure responsible tax behaviors. The expertise and knowledge of directors in tax-related matters also play a critical role. Independent directors with relevant experience and expertise in tax can contribute significantly to the development and implementation of effective tax strategies (Onyali & Okafor, 2018).

2.1.4 CEO duality

CEO duality refers to a governance structure where an individual simultaneously holds the roles of CEO and Chairman of the Board within a company. This concentration of power has both advantages and disadvantages, which may impact various aspects of a firm's operations, including its tax strategies and effective tax rate. Research by Ezejiofor and Ezenwafor, (2020) showed that CEO duality is significant and has a positive coefficient on tax planning of food and beverage companies in Nigeria. This suggests that when one person controls both the executive and oversight functions, there may be less scrutiny and accountability, possibly leading to suboptimal tax governance practices. One potential relationship between CEO duality and the effective tax rate lies in the lack of independent oversight as suggested by (Rezaei & Azimi, 2015).

With limited checks and balances, the CEO may have greater discretion to engage in tax planning strategies that minimize tax liabilities. This could result in lower effective tax rates for conglomerate firms in Nigeria. However, it is important to note that not all firms with CEO duality engage in aggressive tax planning, and the actual impact may vary depending on other factors such as industry dynamics and corporate governance mechanisms (Ezejiofor & Ezenwafor, 2020). Conversely, CEO duality may also have positive implications for tax management. Given their comprehensive understanding of both the operational and strategic aspects of the business, CEOs in dual roles may be better positioned to develop more efficient tax strategies. These strategies can reduce tax burdens, enhance competitiveness, and boost firm performance as suggested by (Ijeoma & Ezejiofor, 2013).

2.1.5 Institutional ownership

Institutional ownership entails the collective ownership of a company's stock by large institutions such as mutual funds, pension funds, insurance companies, and hedge funds. These institutional investors pool together funds from individual and corporate investors to make strategic investment decisions in the stock market. The scale and sophistication of institutional investors allow them to exert considerable influence on the companies in which they invest. Timothy et al. (2020) proposed that one of the key roles played by institutional ownership is that of a steward of corporate governance. Institutions with substantial ownership stakes can wield significant voting power in crucial decisions such as board appointments, executive compensation packages, mergers and acquisitions, and other strategic matters. This influence extends beyond the boardroom, as

institutional investors often engage directly with company management to advocate for shareholder interests and drive improvements in corporate performance as documented by (Zhang et al., 2022). High levels of institutional ownership are often seen as a vote of confidence in a company's prospects and management team. Companies with strong institutional backing may benefit from increased visibility and credibility in the eyes of individual investors, analysts, and other stakeholders. This can have a positive impact on the company's stock price, liquidity, and overall market perception (Makni et al., 2012). However, the concentration of institutional ownership also raises important considerations regarding corporate accountability, transparency, and long-term sustainability. Institutional investors may face conflicts of interest in balancing short-term financial performance with broader social and ethical considerations. Concerns about activist investing, proxy voting practices, and the alignment of institutional interests with those of individual shareholders underscore the complex interplay of incentives and objectives within the realm of institutional ownership (Makni et al., 2012).

According to Jamei (2021), institutional ownership serves as a linchpin of corporate monitoring mechanisms, reshaping the landscape of corporate governance, shareholder activism, and market dynamics for listed conglomerate firms. By navigating the nuances of institutional ownership, companies can forge stronger relationships with their institutional investors, enhance transparency and accountability, and ultimately drive sustainable value creation for their stakeholders.

2.1.6 Board size

Board size refers to the number of directors serving on a company's board of directors. The concept of board size has been a subject of interest and debate in the field of corporate governance, as it influences the dynamics, decision-making processes, and effectiveness of the board in fulfilling its oversight and strategic responsibilities (Makni et al., 2012). The optimal board size is a crucial consideration for companies, as it can impact board performance, director engagement, and overall governance outcomes. Gomes (2016) carefully opined that the debate over board size revolves around finding the right balance between having a board that is large enough to bring diverse perspectives, expertise, and independent oversight, while also being small enough to facilitate effective communication, decision-making, and accountability. Different stakeholders, governance experts, and empirical studies have put forth various arguments regarding the ideal board size, with considerations ranging from the company's size, complexity, industry sector, ownership structure, and regulatory context.

A larger board size can potentially offer a broader range of skills, experiences, and knowledge among directors, which can be beneficial for addressing complex strategic issues, industry-specific challenges, and emerging trends as recorded by (Keung et al., 2017). A diverse set of perspectives on a larger board may lead to more robust discussions, enhanced creativity in problem-solving, and better decision-making processes. Poudel (2015) added that a larger board size may provide for greater representation of key stakeholder interests, such as shareholders, employees, customers, and community members, leading to a more inclusive and socially responsible governance approach. On the other hand, a smaller board size is often associated with greater efficiency, agility, and coherence in board operations. A smaller board may facilitate more focused discussions, quicker decision-making, and stronger relationships among directors, management, and stakeholders (Martinez, 2017). With fewer members, a board can potentially reduce coordination challenges, conflicts of interest, and group dynamics issues that may arise in larger boards. A smaller board size may also enhance individual director accountability, engagement, and contribution to board deliberations and decision-making processes. Yahaya et al., (2023) opined that companies need to consider their unique circumstances, strategic priorities, and governance objectives when determining the appropriate board size that best fits their needs and aligns with their governance strategy.

In practice, boards may vary in size based on industry norms, legal requirements, shareholder preferences, and organizational culture. Some companies may opt for smaller boards to enhance efficiency and agility, while others may choose larger boards to leverage diverse expertise and ensure comprehensive oversight. Board size is a dynamic aspect of corporate governance that may evolve over time in response to changing market conditions, regulatory developments, board refreshment practices, and strategic imperatives. Omesi and Appah, (2021) recorded that the concept of board size underscores the importance of thoughtful board composition, governance structure, and director

dynamics in shaping the effectiveness and performance of a company's board of directors. By carefully considering the implications of board size on board dynamics, decision-making processes, and governance outcomes, companies can enhance their board's ability to provide strategic guidance, monitor performance, manage risks, and create long-term value for all stakeholders (Onyali & Okafor, 2018).

2.1.7 Tax avoidance

Tax avoidance refers to legitimate methods utilized by companies to minimize their tax liabilities within the boundaries of tax laws and regulations. These strategies involve taking advantage of specific provisions, deductions, credits, exemptions, and incentives offered by the tax system (Odukoya et al., 2015). The result of these strategies reflects in the prevailing effective tax rate at any point in time. In the context of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria, tax avoidance can be employed to legally reduce the effective tax rate and maximize after-tax profits. While it is challenging to find specific research on tax avoidance in Nigerian firms, knowledge about these practices can be inferred from general principles and observations in taxation literature (Richardson et al., 2019).

One common tax sheltering strategy is to take advantage of tax incentives provided by the government. Governments often introduce tax incentives to promote certain sectors or activities that contribute to economic growth and development. Companies can strategically plan their operations to qualify for these incentives, such as tax breaks for investing in specific industries or regions (Hulland et al., 2018). Another strategy is to undertake income shifting within multinational corporations. This involves allocating profits to low-tax jurisdictions or using transfer pricing techniques to shift income to subsidiaries located in countries with more favorable tax regimes as suggested by (Umeh et al., 2020). Though this practice aligns with arm's length principles, which is subject to scrutiny by tax authorities. Moreover, companies can engage in debt shifting to reduce their taxable income. By leveraging debt financing, firms can deduct interest expenses, which lowers their taxable profits as reported by (Mosuin et al., 2025).

2.1.8 Effective tax rate

The effective tax rate (ETR) is an important measure used to assess a company's tax burden relative to its pre-tax profits. In the context of tax avoidance, the ETR can be influenced by corporate monitoring mechanisms employed by listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. These mechanisms help ensure transparency, accountability, and adherence to tax compliance policies, thus reducing potential tax avoidance or evasion. One corporate monitoring mechanism that can affect the ETR is the presence of an independent board of directors or audit committee. These oversight bodies are responsible for reviewing financial statements, including tax provisions, and ensuring compliance with tax laws (Nwaorgu et al., 2020). Through their scrutiny, they can discourage aggressive tax planning or the use of questionable tax avoidance. Additionally, effective internal control systems play a vital role in monitoring and managing the tax function. Internal controls encompass processes, policies, and procedures that safeguard assets, ensure accurate financial reporting, and promote compliance with laws and regulations (Zalata & Roberts, 2016). Robust internal controls related to tax functions can help prevent inadvertent errors, reduce the risk of non-compliance, and enhance the accuracy of tax calculations, ultimately impacting the ETR.

2.1.9 The relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and effective tax rate

The relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms, such as audit committee size, board independence, CEO duality, institutional ownership and board size and the effective tax rate (ETR) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria is an important aspect to consider in understanding the impact of these mechanisms on tax management practices.

Audit committee size can influence the ETR by providing more resources and expertise to oversee tax-related matters. Research suggests that larger audit committees are associated with improved tax compliance and reduced tax aggressiveness. A larger committee allows for greater specialization, enabling more rigorous scrutiny of tax positions and potentially deterring the use of aggressive tax avoidance (

Board independence, defined as the proportion of independent directors on the board, is another crucial mechanism that can affect the ETR. Independent directors bring impartiality and objectivity to the decision-making process, reducing the likelihood of tax avoidance or evasion. Ogbeide and Osaretin (2018) documented a negative association between board independence and tax

aggressiveness. Greater board independence enhances monitoring and oversight, leading to improved tax compliance and potentially lowering the ETR.

CEO duality may also have positive implications for tax management. Given their comprehensive understanding of both the operational and strategic aspects of the business, CEOs in dual roles may be better positioned to develop more efficient tax strategies. These strategies can reduce tax burdens, enhance competitiveness, and boost firm performance as suggested by Poudel, (2015).

2.1.10 Audit committee size and effective tax rate

Poudel, (2015) x-rayed that the size of an audit committee within a company's corporate monitoring mechanism is closely linked to its effective tax rate, reflecting the intricate interplay between financial oversight, regulatory compliance, and tax management strategies. The audit committee, typically composed of independent directors responsible for supervising financial reporting practices and internal controls, plays a crucial role in ensuring transparency, integrity, and accountability in tax-related matters. The relationship between audit committee size and effective tax rate underscores the importance of robust governance mechanisms in influencing tax planning decisions and tax-related outcomes as proposed by Desai and Dharmapala, (2019). A larger audit committee size can enhance the effectiveness of tax oversight and compliance efforts within a listed conglomerate firm. A diverse and well-qualified audit committee with a sufficient number of members may bring a broader range of expertise, industry knowledge, and independent perspectives to bear on tax-related issues. This can lead to more comprehensive reviews of tax planning strategies, increased scrutiny of tax risk management practices, and improved alignment with regulatory requirements and accounting standards (Makni et al., 2012).

Furthermore, a larger audit committee size can facilitate greater transparency and accountability in tax-related decision-making processes. With more members available to review tax positions, assess tax implications of strategic initiatives, and evaluate potential tax risks, the audit committee can provide more robust oversight and challenge management's tax-related assumptions and practices (Makni et al., 2012). This can help mitigate the risk of aggressive tax planning schemes, tax avoidance strategies that push the boundaries of legality, or non-compliance with tax laws and regulations (Makni et al., 2012). The significance of audit committee size in influencing the effective tax rate of a conglomerate firm lies in its ability to promote sound governance practices, foster a culture of compliance, and enhance stakeholder trust. A well-structured and adequately sized audit committee can serve as a critical safeguard against tax-related missteps, financial irregularities, and reputational risks stemming from inadequate tax governance. By maintaining an appropriate balance of skills, experience, and independence on the audit committee, companies can strengthen their tax management capabilities and navigate complex tax environments with greater confidence (Malik et al., 2014).

The relationship between audit committee size and effective tax rate operates through a series of mechanisms that shape the company's approach to tax planning, reporting, and risk management. A larger audit committee size allows for more in-depth discussions, deliberations, and reviews of tax-related matters during committee meetings, enhancing the level of scrutiny and due diligence applied to tax-related decisions. This, in turn, can lead to more accurate tax reporting, better identification of tax opportunities, and enhanced compliance with tax laws and regulations (Makni et al., 2012).

Minnick and Noga, (2020) added that the relationship between audit committee size and effective tax rate underscores the pivotal role of corporate governance in shaping tax outcomes and ensuring tax practices align with ethical standards, regulatory expectations, and shareholder interests. By recognizing the synergies between audit committee effectiveness and tax performance, listed conglomerate firms can leverage their governance structures to achieve tax efficiency, mitigate tax risks, and uphold transparency and integrity in their tax affairs.

2.1.11 Board independence and effective tax rate

The relationship between board independence and the effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria is a critical aspect of corporate mechanism that influences tax planning, compliance, and financial transparency. Board independence refers to the composition of a company's board of directors with a majority of independent directors who are not affiliated with the management or significant shareholders of the firm. In the Nigerian context, the independence of the board is crucial for ensuring impartial oversight, enhancing accountability, and safeguarding shareholder interests in

tax-related matters as reported by Omesi and Appah, (2021). Gomes, (2016) postulated that a board with a higher level of independence is likely to exercise stronger oversight over tax planning strategies, tax risk management practices, and tax compliance efforts within a listed conglomerate firm. Independent directors bring objectivity, diverse perspectives, and a commitment to upholding ethical standards and regulatory compliance in tax-related decision-making processes. Their independence from management interests reduces the risk of conflicts of interest and ensures that tax-related decisions are scrutinized impartially, with a focus on long-term value creation and risk mitigation (Timothy et al., 2020).

In the Nigerian business environment, where tax regulations can be complex and subject to evolving compliance requirements, the presence of independent directors on the board can contribute to a more robust governance framework for addressing tax-related challenges (Minnick & Noga, 2020). Independent directors can provide valuable expertise, guidance, and oversight on tax policy formulation, tax planning strategies, and tax reporting practices, helping to enhance the effectiveness of the company's tax management processes and reduce the likelihood of tax-related controversies or reputational risks. Poudel, (2015) opined that board independence plays a crucial role in promoting transparency and accountability in tax matters, which can impact the effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. An independent board is better positioned to evaluate the company's tax positions, assess the appropriateness of tax strategies, and ensure that tax-related disclosures are accurate and comprehensive. By fostering a culture of openness, integrity, and compliance with tax laws and regulations, independent directors can help enhance stakeholder trust and confidence in the company's tax governance practices (Minnick & Noga, 2020).

The relationship between board independence and effective tax rate operates through a series of mechanisms that influence the company's approach to tax planning, reporting, and compliance (Jamei, 2021). A board with a higher level of independence is more likely to establish strong governance structures, tax oversight mechanisms, and internal controls that support prudent tax management and alignment with regulatory requirements. Independent directors may also challenge management assumptions, review tax-related risks, and hold executives accountable for tax-related decisions, contributing to a more disciplined and responsible approach to tax matters. Martinez, (2017) summarized that the relationship between board independence and effective tax rate in listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria underscores the importance of sound corporate governance practices in shaping tax outcomes, promoting compliance, and enhancing transparency and accountability. By cultivating a culture of independence, diligence, and ethical behavior at the board level, Nigerian companies can strengthen their tax governance frameworks, mitigate tax risks, and uphold high standards of integrity in their tax affairs, ultimately contributing to sustainable growth and value creation for all stakeholders (Egbunike et al., 2015).

2.1.12 CEO duality and effective tax rate

The relationship between CEO duality and the effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria is an important area of study that can shed light on the impact of corporate monitoring practices on tax management strategies and financial performance. In the context of the Nigerian business environment, where conglomerate firms operate in diverse sectors and face complex regulatory and tax compliance challenges, the relationship between CEO duality and the effective tax rate can be influenced by several factors. Research by Poudel, (2015) alongside Yahaya et al., (2023) suggested that CEO duality may have both positive and negative effects on a firm's tax management practices and tax-related outcomes.

On one hand, CEO duality can lead to concentrated power and decision-making authority in the hands of a single individual, potentially resulting in a lack of checks and balances in corporate governance processes. This concentration of power may increase the likelihood of conflicts of interest, self-serving behaviors, and weaker oversight of tax planning and reporting activities, which could impact the effective tax rate of conglomerate firms (Kabir & Jahedi, 2017). Zalata and Roberts, (2016) supported that inadequate monitoring and accountability mechanisms in the presence of CEO duality may result in a higher tax burden for the firm, as tax optimization strategies may not be effectively implemented or aligned with shareholder interests. On the other hand, CEO duality could also enhance coordination, alignment, and efficiency in strategic decision-making, including tax management strategies, within conglomerate firms. A unified leadership structure under a dually

appointed CEO and board chair may facilitate quicker responses to tax planning opportunities, clearer communication of tax-related priorities, and faster implementation of tax-saving initiatives (Umeh et al., 2020). This streamlined decision-making process could lead to a lower effective tax rate for the firm, as it can optimize tax planning efforts, reduce tax liabilities, and enhance overall tax performance (Kabir & Jahedi, 2017).

The relationship between CEO duality and effective tax rate in listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria is likely to be influenced by contextual factors such as the firm's industry sector, size, ownership structure, corporate culture, regulatory environment, and external market conditions as opined by Hulland et al., (2018) alongside Husninet al., (2016). It is important for researchers and practitioners to conduct in-depth analyses and case studies to understand how CEO duality impacts tax strategies, tax compliance behavior, tax-related risks, and financial outcomes in the Nigerian conglomerate context as reported by (Edame & Okoi, 2014). The interplay between CEO duality and effective tax rate underscores the significance of sound corporate governance practices, transparency, accountability, and ethical leadership in guiding tax-related decisions and behaviors within conglomerate firms. By examining the nuances of this relationship, stakeholders can better appreciate the complexities of governance structures, executive leadership dynamics, and tax management strategies that shape the tax performance and financial health of listed conglomerates in Nigeria (Emeakaroha, 2019).

2.1.13 Institutional ownership and effective tax rate

The connectives between institutional ownership and effective tax rate is complex and multifaceted. Institutional investors often have diverse investment objectives, risk preferences, and governance expectations that shape their influence on tax-related decisions within conglomerate firms. High levels of institutional ownership may exert pressure on firms to adopt tax-efficient practices, enhance transparency in tax reporting, and align tax strategies with long-term value creation (Hashim et al., 2014). Goh et al., (2016) opined that institutional investors typically conduct due diligence on a firm's tax practices and compliance efforts, as part of their evaluation of investment risks and returns. They may engage directly with management and board members to raise concerns or provide guidance on tax-related matters, including the effective tax rate. This engagement process can lead to improved tax governance, enhanced tax risk management, and greater accountability in tax planning processes as x-rayed by Mosuin et al. (2025)

The presence of institutional investors with differing priorities and preferences can also create challenges for listed conglomerate firms in managing their effective tax rate (Hashim et al., 2014). Institutional owners may pursue short-term profit objectives or demand higher returns on investment, which could incentivize firms to prioritize aggressive tax planning strategies that minimize tax expenses in the short term but increase tax-related risks and controversies in the long run (Fagbemi et al., 2019). According to Koester et al., (2020) and Richardson et al., (2019), institutional investors may have varying levels of expertise, resources, and influence in monitoring and shaping a firm's tax policies. Firms with a diverse shareholder base of institutional owners may face complexities in balancing competing demands, meeting disclosure requirements, and addressing divergent perspectives on tax optimization versus tax compliance.

In navigating the relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate, conglomerate firms in Nigeria must consider the importance of maintaining open communication channels with institutional investors, fostering a culture of responsible tax governance, and integrating tax considerations into strategic decision-making processes (Goh et al., 2016). By proactively engaging with institutional owners, disclosing relevant tax information, and adopting best practices in tax risk management, conglomerate firms can strengthen their tax performance, enhance investor confidence, and sustain long-term value creation (Hashim et al., 2014). The interplay between institutional ownership dynamics and effective tax rate underscores the critical role of corporate mechanism, investor relations, and stakeholder engagement in shaping tax strategies and outcomes for listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria (Kabir & Jahedi, 2017). Edame and Okoi, (2014) postulated that by cultivating a collaborative and transparent relationship with institutional investors, firms can better align their tax practices with investor expectations, regulatory requirements, and sustainable business objectives, thereby promoting financial health, compliance integrity, and stakeholder trust in the Nigerian corporate landscape.

2.1.14 Board size and effective tax rate

Board size is a pivotal aspect of corporate mechanism within listed conglomerate firms, playing a significant role in shaping the dynamics of strategic decision-making, oversight, and accountability. Umeh et al., (2020) alongside Husnin et al., (2016) recorded that the composition and structure of a company's board of directors, including the number of members, can have far-reaching implications for its operational efficiency, risk management practices, and overall performance. The concept of board size assumes critical importance as a determinant of governance effectiveness and regulatory compliance (Hashim et al., 2014). The size of a company's board of directors refers to the total number of individuals who serve as members of the board. The composition of the board typically includes a mix of executive directors (e.g., CEO, CFO) and non-executive directors (independent directors, outside experts), with the latter category often representing a majority of board members in modern corporate governance structures (Goh et al., 2016). The decision regarding board size is influenced by a variety of factors, including the company's size, industry complexity, regulatory requirements, and strategic objectives.

Richardson et al., (2019) reported that from a governance perspective, board size plays a key role in determining the board's ability to fulfill its oversight responsibilities effectively. A larger board may offer a broader range of expertise, diverse perspectives, and independent viewpoints, which can enhance the quality of decision-making and strategic guidance provided to the company's management team. Moreover, a larger board size may facilitate more robust monitoring of management actions, increased scrutiny of financial reporting practices, and greater accountability in terms of risk management and compliance with regulatory standards (Hashim et al., 2014). Conversely, an excessively large board size can present challenges in terms of efficiency, coordination, and group dynamics (Hashim et al., 2014). Boards that are too large may struggle to reach timely decisions, maintain effective communication channels, or foster a cohesive governance culture. This can lead to potential conflicts of interest, power struggles among board members, and a dilution of individual accountability for board decisions (Koester et al., 2020). In the context of tax avoidance strategies, the size of the board may also influence the company's ability to implement effective tax planning measures, mitigate tax risks, and comply with evolving tax regulations as supported by (Edame & Okoi, 2014).

In the realm of corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance strategies for listed conglomerate firms, the optimal board size represents a delicate balance between diversity, expertise, efficiency, and accountability (Fagbemi et al., 2019). By carefully considering the implications of board size on governance practices, shareholder value creation, and long-term sustainability, companies can enhance their capacity to navigate complex tax environments, mitigate tax-related risks, and uphold high standards of corporate transparency and integrity (Hashim et al., 2014).

2.2 Theoretical framework

In the course of this study, institutional theory by Meyer and Rowan, (1977), the Signalling theory by Michael Spence, (1973) and the stewardship theory by Davis, Schoorman, and Donaldson, (1997) will be reviewed.

2.2.1 Institutional theory by Meyer and Rowan, (1977)

Institutional theory, propounded by John Meyer and Brian Rowan in 1977, focuses on how organizations conform to and are influenced by social and institutional norms. This theory is relevant for understanding the corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. According to Institutional Theory, organizations are shaped by external forces, including societal rules, norms, and expectations (Meyer & Rowan, 1977). These external pressures influence organizational behavior and decision-making, including tax management practices and corporate monitoring mechanisms, to ensure conformity with institutional norms. The Institutional environment plays a crucial role in shaping tax avoidance in listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. These organizations respond to pressures from various stakeholders such as the government, tax authorities, investors, customers, and the wider society (Oluseyi et al., 2019).

To maintain legitimacy and avoid sanctions or reputational damage, firms develop tax avoidance that align with prevailing institutional norms and expectations regarding responsible tax practices. One key aspect of institutional theory relevant to this research is isomorphism, which refers to the tendency of organizations to mimic or adopt similar structures and practices as their peers in order to

gain acceptance and legitimacy (Hashim et al., 2014). In the context of tax avoidance, conglomerate firms in Nigeria may engage in mimetic isomorphism, where they imitate the tax practices of other successful firms in their industry. This imitation can be driven by the desire to conform, gain legitimacy, or simply reduce uncertainty (Agbebi et al., 2016). The theory highlights isomorphism, regulative, normative, and cognitive pressures as key factors shaping firms' tax practices. To maintain legitimacy, firms adopt tax avoidance that align with institutional norms, while implementing corporate monitoring mechanisms to assure stakeholders of their compliance with legal and ethical tax obligations. This theory is relevance to this study because in Nigeria. the institutional context (like tax laws, corporate governance codes, and regulatory enforcement) can influence how conglomerate firms design their corporate monitoring mechanisms and approach tax compliance.

2.2.2 The Signalling theory by Michael Spence, (1973)

The signaling theory was propounded by Spence in 1973. Spence, (1973) suggested that companies use various signals to convey information to stakeholders about their financial health, governance quality, and future prospects. The theory proposes that listed conglomerate firms may use tax avoidance as a signal to stakeholders, such as investors, regulators, and the general public, about their financial performance and governance quality. Agbebi et al., (2016) added that by engaging in tax avoidance strategies, firms may be signaling that they are financially healthy and able to exploit tax loopholes, or that they have a sophisticated and aggressive tax planning strategy in place. Conversely, firms that do not engage in tax avoidance may be signaling that they are transparent, compliant, and committed to good governance.

The relevance of Signaling theory to this study lies in its ability to explain why listed conglomerate firms may engage in tax avoidance, despite the potential risks and negative consequences. By examining the signaling role of tax avoidance, this study can gain insights into the motivations and incentives of firms to engage in tax avoidance, and how corporate monitoring mechanisms can influence these behaviors.

2.2.3 The stewardship theory by Davis and Donaldson, (1997)

The stewardship theory was propounded by Davis and Danaldson in 1997. Davis and Donaldson, (1997) proposes that managers are stewards of the company's resources and are motivated to act in the best interests of shareholders. According to Davis and Donaldson (1997), managers are driven by a sense of responsibility, loyalty, and duty to maximize shareholder value. In the context of this research topic, Stewardship theory suggests that managers of listed conglomerate firms are expected to act as responsible stewards of corporate resources, including financial resources, and make decisions that promote the long-term interests of shareholders (Goh et al.,2016). In relation to tax avoidance, Stewardship theory implies that managers who adopt a stewardship approach will prioritize transparency, compliance, and good governance over aggressive tax planning strategies. They will recognize that tax avoidance can damage the company's reputation, lead to regulatory scrutiny, and ultimately harm shareholder value. Therefore, managers who embody the stewardship ethos will be more likely to adopt conservative tax strategies that balance the need to minimize tax liabilities with the need to maintain a positive reputation and comply with regulatory requirements (Davis & Donaldson, 1997).

The relevance of Stewardship theory to this study lies in its ability to provide insights into the motivations and behaviors of managers in listed conglomerate firms. By examining the stewardship orientation of managers, this study can gain a deeper understanding of why some firms engage in tax avoidance while others do not, and how corporate monitoring mechanisms can influence managerial decisions related to tax planning.

2.3 Empirical review

The following empirical were reviewed:

Mosuin et al. (2025) examined the impact of corporate governance monitoring mechanisms on tax avoidance. Many countries rely on taxes as their primary source of revenue to raise budget revenues and fund national development. Taxation performs numerous functions by favourably influencing a country's investment, education, social and economic development. Nevertheless, tax authorities require assistance with the problem of tax non-compliance, which hinders tax collection and administration. Tax avoidance is a tactic that businesses use to limit their tax liabilities by taking advantage of legal gaps in tax legislation. This study aims to determine how corporate governance

monitoring systems affect tax avoidance. A secondary data analysis will be carried out based on the reported financial statements of Malaysian listed firms from 2018 to 2022 (5 years). The data for this investigation are analysed using STATA software. The findings of this study show that corporate social responsibility has a weak, significant negative impact on tax avoidance, and foreign ownership has a weak, significant positive impact on tax avoidance. Meanwhile, leverage (control variable) shows a significant positive impact on tax avoidance.

Lv et al. (2025) evaluate the impact and moderating mechanism of corporate tax avoidance on firm value from the perspective of corporate governance. Drawing upon data from Shanghai and Shenzhen A-share listed companies from 2012 to 2022, this study investigates the impact of corporate tax avoidance on firm value in various settings. The findings reveal that tax avoidance can reduce firm value. Nonetheless, high-quality internal control mechanisms reduce the negative impact of tax avoidance on firm value. Furthermore, increasing the proportion of independent directors effectively mitigates the detrimental effects of tax avoidance on firm value. Notably, the negative impact of tax avoidance on firm value is more pronounced when institutional investors' shareholding ratios are lower, emphasizing the importance of diverse governance structures in risk management. The study provides important insights for policymakers, corporate managers, and investors, suggesting that improving corporate governance and internal control systems is critical for promoting long-term firm value and mitigating the negative effects of tax avoidance.

Koay and Sapiei, (2025) examined the role of corporate governance on corporate tax avoidance from the developing country perspective of Malaysia. A sample of 318 firm-year observations from 2016 to 2020 from the 100 largest listed companies in Malaysia was analysed using a fixed effects panel least squares regression model. CEOs play a significant role in corporate tax avoidance in Malaysia. Specifically, they are motivated by money and power to engage in risky tax avoidance activity. It was also found that corporate governance mechanisms related to the board of directors have a limited effect on companies' tax compliance issues. This study's findings can help regulators and policymakers understand the circumstances leading to increased tax aggressiveness as well as the limitations of certain governance mechanisms in curbing tax avoidance activity within companies. The findings can also assist shareholders and investors in formulating internal policies to create better alignment of their interests with those of management. The unique emerging economy evidence and insights from this study advance knowledge and can inspire fellow researchers in their future studies.

Mosuin et al. (2024) carried out a conceptual review on the effect of corporate governance monitoring mechanisms on tax avoidance. Taxes are the primary source of revenue for many nations in order to increase budget revenues and fund national development. Taxation serves multiple purposes because it can positively impact a nation's investment, education, social and economic development. However, tax authorities require assistance with the issue of tax non-compliance, which impedes tax administration and collection. One of the categories of tax non-compliance is tax avoidance, which is one of the company's strategies for legally reducing its tax burden by exploiting loopholes in tax regulations to minimise tax liability. Tax avoidance is when a company follows a particular tax strategy in the hopes that the tax measures will not be legally audited or questioned, but the action is risky if the tax methods are considered unlawful. Although the implementation of corporate governance practices within listed firms, the issue of corporate taxation revenues in Malaysia remains a cause for concern, as they constitute a significant portion of the government's overall income collection. Therefore, effective governance practices may offer improved tax avoidance oversight among Malaysian companies which in turn improve the company's integrity and in line with the national SDGs agenda. However, embedding good governance practices among common governance mechanism studies in monitoring tax avoidance is still scarce, particularly in an emerging country, Malaysia. This study investigates the impact of corporate governance monitoring mechanisms on tax avoidance. The secondary data analysis will be conducted based on the reported financial statements by Malaysian listed companies from 2018 until 2022 (5 years). STATA Software will be used to analyse the data for this study. The findings of this study may show how the corporate governance monitoring mechanisms determine whether a company's management operates in the best interests of its shareholders and whether tax avoidance options are utilised in the shareholders' best interests.

Salehi et al. (2024) examined the impact of corporate governance on tax avoidance. We employ three proxies to measure tax avoidance or tax management within companies listed on the Tehran Stock

Exchange (TSE). The CG mechanisms under scrutiny encompass board size and independence, CEO duality, auditor type, common stock ratio of at least 5% to total stock, managers' common stock holdings about total stock, gender diversity, manager ownership value, board meeting frequency, CEO stock ownership percentage, institutional shareholders' stock holdings, audit committee membership, and financial specialization. This research investigates 192 companies listed on the TSE, utilizing data available on the TSE website from 2011 to 2021. Our findings indicate that while several CG mechanisms, such as board size and independence, audit firm size, gender diversity, institutional ownership, and the specialization of audit committee members, serve to reduce tax avoidance, CEO duality exacerbates it. Moreover, profitability, financial leverage, and capital significantly inhibit tax avoidance. In contrast, the return on assets (ROA), economic growth, and inflation have a pronounced positive association with tax avoidance.

Guo et al. (2024) examined corporate governance effects of digital finance: Evidence from corporate tax avoidance in China. This paper tries to uncover the corporate governance effects of digital finance based on the corporate tax avoidance perspective. We find strong evidence that digital finance is negatively associated with corporate tax avoidance. The governance role digital finance plays is primarily mediated through the mechanisms of resource allocation and information governance effects. Further analysis shows that the negative effects of digital finance are more pronounced among higher profitability and non-state-owned firms. Additionally, multiple major shareholders and stronger internal control quality (corporate internal governance) as well as higher institutional investor shareholding and more analyst attention (corporate external governance) can strengthen their negative connection, manifesting the complementarity between digital finance and modern corporate governance mechanisms. Overall, this paper reveals the spillover effects of changes in the financial development environment on corporate tax avoidance strategies. It also contributes to enriching the literature on the corporate governance value of digital finance and the factors influencing corporate tax avoidance.

Ismail et al. (2024) aims to theoretically investigate the effect of activating corporate governance (CG) mechanisms on the association between adopting corporate social responsibility (CSR) and tax avoidance (TA). Based on the analyzing of the previous studies, the authors support the results of studies that found a positive effect for activating CG on the adoption of CSR. Also, they found that there is a negative impact of activating CG mechanisms on TA, as CG includes controls and procedures that contribute to limiting opportunistic behaviors of management and ensures making decisions that maximize value for shareholders. To the best of the authors' knowledge, it is the only chapter that examines the effect of activating CG mechanisms on the association between CSR and TA.

Guo et al. (2023) examined how institutional investors' corporate site visits affect tax avoidance. Using quantile regressions, we find that corporate site visits decrease tax avoidance for firms at high levels of tax avoidance and increase tax avoidance for firms at low levels. The effect of corporate site visits on tax avoidance is stronger for firms subject to a weaker information environment, which suggests that institutional investors acquire additional firm-specific information via corporate site visits and play a more effective monitoring role. We also find that visitors who visited low-tax firms in prior years share tax-planning knowledge with high-tax firms which they visit in the current year. The effect of tax knowledge transfer is more pronounced when the visitors are from incumbent institutional shareholders. This study identifies corporate site visits as a channel via which institutional investors serve as monitors to managers and as facilitators of tax knowledge transfer.

Bash and Zoghalmi, (2023) evaluate the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on tax avoidance practices. This research came with the aim of showing the impact of governance mechanisms on tax avoidance practices, and in light of this, the financial data of the joint stock companies (industrial, service, agricultural, and hotels) listed in the Iraq Stock Exchange amounting to (35) companies were collected during the period (2009-2020). Through the financial reports published on the market website, multiple linear regression analysis was used as a tool to study the relationship between variables, and (Eviews 12) program was used for analysis and hypothesis testing. To achieve the objectives of the research, (administrative ownership, board size, board independence, women's membership) was adopted as an indicator of the dimensions of governance, and tax avoidance was measured through the effective tax rate. The research concluded that there is a positive

impact of administrative ownership and women's membership on tax avoidance practices, as confirmed there is no effect of board size and independence on tax avoidance. The research has reached a set of conclusions, the most important of which are: The method of applying governance mechanisms is one of the main pillars in enhancing competitive capabilities and reorganizing companies' businesses to help them achieve their goals and those of their clients. The research presented a number of recommendations, the most prominent of which were: the necessity of developing a legal and regulatory framework in Iraq that governs the work of joint-stock companies listed within the Iraq Stock Exchange in light of the preparation of principles and mechanisms for governance in a clear and explicit way, to reduce the negative effects and opportunistic practices associated with tax avoidance, and in a manner that is compatible with developments in the financial and legal environment.

Kustono et al. (2023) aimed to examine the causes of tax avoidance in the hospitality sub-sectors based on political costs and monitoring mechanisms. Data were collected from the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2014-2021 reporting period, resulting in 168 firm-year observations. Nine hypotheses were tested using variant-based SEM with Partial Least Square. The results showed that political costs, monitoring mechanisms, financing decisions, and financial distress influenced tax avoidance choices in stable conditions. Different results were found during the pandemic, only political costs and financial distress affected tax avoidance. These findings could help stakeholders in decision-making by understanding the indicators of their tendencies. Mediating effects tests found no intervention function in this relationship. The implications in practice regarding the antecedents of tax avoidance in stable or unstable conditions as signals for stakeholders to assess the company's prospects in any situation. As a government, these signals can be used to create a society's interest protector.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design. This design is suitable because the data for the analysis had already transpired, leaving no room for the researcher to manipulate the variables under study.

3.2 Population of the study

This study is anchor on the six (6) conglomerate firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2014 to 2023. As such, the population of the study stood at 6. The conglomerate firms are as follows: Chellarams plc, Custodian investment plc, John Holt plc, SCOA Nig. Plc, Transnational corporation plc and UACN plc.

These firms were selected because they are the major players in the economy. Their tax practices can significantly affect government revenue. Therefore, studying these firms can provide insights into how corporate monitoring mechanisms influences tax avoidance in Nigeria.

3.3 Sample size and sample size determination

All the six (6) listed conglomerate firms are considered in the course of this study. This implies that the population and the sample size is the same, that is, six (6).

3.4 Sampling technique

This study employed census sampling technique. This is because the population is sizeable enough to study without drawing any sample out of it.

3.5 Sources of data and method of data collection

The data for the dependent and independent variables was extracted from financial reports using content analysis methods and was compiled using Microsoft Excel software. The study employed a panel data methodology, which is deem suitable for the analysis. A total of 60 pooled observations was obtained, consisting of 6 cross-sectional observations for each year and ten time-series observations for each conglomerate firm regressor and explained variable. The use of panel data allows for more informative data, increased degrees of freedom, enhanced efficiency, and enables the examination of fixed and random effects in longitudinal data sets (Gujarati et al., 2012).

3.6 Method of data analysis

The study adopted multiple regression in analyzing the data via Eviews 10.0. The data conformed to the standardized regression assumptions, that is, linearity, homoscedasticity, normality and

independence of data. Durbin Watson statistics is within the range of 1-3, (Gujarati *et al.*, 2012). The decision was based on 5% level of significance. Accept null hypothesis (Ho) if probability value (i.e. P-value or Sig.) is greater than or equals to (\geq) stated 5% level of significance (α); otherwise, reject and accept alternate hypothesis (H₁), if p-value or sig. calculated is less than 5% level of significance.

3.7 Model specification

To achieve the stated objectives of the study, as well as testing the study hypotheses, a multiple linear regression model was adopted as follows;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \mu \dots\dots\dots eqn 1.$$

Where;

Y = Tax avoidance (dependent variable)

X = corporate monitoring mechanisms (explanatory/independent variable)

Explicitly, the equation will be defined as:

Tax avoidance = $f(\text{Corporate monitoring mechanisms}) + \mu$

Therefore, the broad model for this study will be modified as;

$$ETR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AUDCSz_{it} + \beta_2 BODI_{it} + \beta_3 CEOD_{it} + \beta_4 INSWH_{it} + \beta_5 BODS_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots eqn 2.$$

Where;

ETR_{it} = Effective tax rate of firm *i* in period *t*

$AUDS_{z_{it}}$ = Audit committee size of firm *i* in period *t*

$BODI_{it}$ = Board independence of firm *i* in period *t*

$CEOD_{it}$ = CEO duality of firm *i* in period *t*

$INSWH_{it}$ = Institutional ownership of firm *i* in period *t*

$BODS_{it}$ = Board size of firm *i* in period *t*

β_0 = Intercept or regression constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_5$ = Regression coefficients to be estimated for firm *i* in period *t*

μ = Stochastic error term.

3.8 Measurement/operationalization of variables

\Table 3.1 below depicts the measurement of the variables defined in the model above.

Table 3.1 Operationalization of variables

Concept	Proxy	Measurement	Source
Corporate monitoring mechanisms (Independent variable)	Audit committee size	Total number of members in firm’s audit committee	Ogbodo and Omonigho (2021) and Agbebi <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	Board independence	Board independence is computed as the proportion of non-executive directors to total directors.	Chytis, Tasios, Filos (2020) and Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021)
	CEO duality	Takes the value of 1 if CEO and the chairperson positions are held by the same individual, 0 otherwise in the period (t).	Ogbodo and Omonigho (2021) and Oyenike, Olayinka and Emeni (2016).
	Institutional ownership	Institutional ownership is computed as the percentage of shares held by institutional investors.	Ogbodo and Omonigho (2021) and Oyenike, Olayinka and Emeni (2016).
	Board size	Board size is computed as the total number of directors on the board	Ogbodo and Omonigho (2021) and Oyenike, Olayinka and Emeni (2016).
Tax avoidance (Dependent variable)	Effective tax rate	This is the proportion of the profit before tax paid as tax. It is computed as tax paid divided by profit before tax.	Ogbodo and Omonigho (2021) and Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021).

Source: Author’s conceptualization, (2025).

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Data presentation

The data for this study is presented in table 4.1(see Appendix I). The data comprise a panel data of sixty (60) pooled observations across six (6) listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria for ten (10)-year period (2014-2023). The data include the dependent variable – Effective tax rate (ETR) and the independent variables which were Audit committee size (AUDCSz), Board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

4.2 Data analysis

Various statistical techniques were utilized in the analysis of data presented in table 4.1 (see Appendix II). These include descriptive statistics, regression assumption tests and panel multiple regression analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive statistics

The result for the descriptive statistics analysis is as presented in Table 4.2 below;

	ETR	AUDCSZ	BODI	CEOD	INSWH	BODS
Mean	0.070264	5.633333	0.734493	0.083333	2.846146	8.200000
Median	0.218613	6.000000	0.750000	0.000000	0.585732	8.000000
Maximum	5.937771	7.000000	0.800000	1.000000	38.45415	11.00000
Minimum	-6.513889	5.000000	0.625000	0.000000	0.014508	5.000000
Std. Dev.	1.362189	0.551321	0.050781	0.278718	6.756372	1.459045
Skewness	-0.947205	0.069811	-0.909323	3.015113	3.601500	-0.186218
Kurtosis	16.48709	2.136745	2.687290	10.09091	16.42217	3.258875
Jarque-Bera	463.7256	1.911759	8.513148	216.6116	580.0944	0.514311
Probability	0.000000	0.384474	0.014171	0.000000	0.000000	0.773248
Sum	4.215834	338.0000	44.06959	5.000000	170.7687	492.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	109.4779	17.93333	0.152146	4.583333	2693.265	125.6000
Observations	60	60	60	60	60	60

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The results in table 4.2 above indicates that effective tax rate (ETR), audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria have mean scores of approximately 0.07, 5.63, 0.73, 0.08, 2.846 and 8 respectively. This indicates the central or average values for these variables from 2014 to 2023. The median values obtained for effective tax rate (ETR), audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria were approximately 0.21, 6.00, 0.75, 0, 0.58 and 8 respectively. These constituted the middle values for the distributions of these variables under the period covered in this study (2014-2023).

In terms of the level of variability and dispersion in the distribution of these variables, the standard deviations obtained for effective tax rate (ETR), audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria were approximately 1.36, 0.55, 0.05, 0.28, 6.75 and 1.46 respectively. This indicates varying levels of variability in the distribution with effective tax rate (ETR) indicating high variations in the distributions. Similarly, the skewness values obtained for effective tax rate (ETR), audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria were -0.94, 0.06, -0.91, 3.015, 3.60 and -0.186. This quantifies the asymmetry of the distributions.

In addition, the kurtosis values obtained for effective tax rate (ETR), audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria were given as approximately 16.48, 2.14, 2.69, 10.09 and 16.42 respectively. Since the values of the kurtosis are greater than zero (0), it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, hence the presence of outliers in the data.

4.2.2 Model evaluation

Residual and coefficient diagnostics were however conducted to assess the suitability of the model as stated in the previous section. These include normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

4.2.2.1 Normality test

Fig. 4.1 Jarque-Bera Normality test results

Source: E-views 10.0 (Output in Appendix II)

The Jarque-Bera test was employed in this case. As applied, if the p-value associated with the Jarque-Bera test is below a predetermined significance level ($p < 0.05$), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data do not follow a normal distribution pattern. With a p-value of 0.069230, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the data were normally distributed.

4.2.2.2 Multicollinearity test

In examining the association among the variables, the study employed the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (correlation matrix), and the results are as presented in the table below.

Table 4.3 Spearman's rank correlation matrix

	ETR	AUDCSZ	BODI	CEOD	INSWH	BODS
ETR	1.000000	-0.236352	-0.041582	-0.099410	0.071125	-0.128660
AUDCSZ	-0.236352	1.000000	0.034557	0.091917	-0.305624	0.155922
BODI	-0.041582	0.034557	1.000000	-0.090105	0.040877	0.189725
CEOD	-0.099410	0.091917	-0.090105	1.000000	-0.098522	-0.041679
INSWH	0.071125	-0.305624	0.040877	-0.098522	1.000000	-0.094746
BODS	-0.128660	0.155922	0.189725	-0.041679	-0.094746	1.000000

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The correlation analysis showed that all independent variables- audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria over the period under study had coefficients lesser than 0.80 respectively confirming absence of multicollinearity issues.

4.2.2.3 Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4.4 Cross-section dependence/ Heteroscedasticity test

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	18.08857	15	0.2580
Pesaran scaled LM	-0.531551		0.5950
Pesaran CD	-0.339564		0.7342

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The statistics and probability value associated with the Breusch-Pagan LM test otherwise known as the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test help determine whether there is evidence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) suggests evidence against the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis which indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. With a p-value of 0.2580, there is sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis, thus, conclude that the predictor variables in the regression model are homoscedastic.

4.3 Test of hypotheses

Each of the hypotheses in this study was tested based on the result obtained from the panel multiple regression analysis. The result that relate to these hypotheses is as summarized in table 4.5 below;

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.312063	3.180065	4.355967	0.0000
AUDCSZ	0.534338	0.344313	3.551896	0.0165
BODI	0.627341	3.600409	4.174241	0.0023
CEOD	-0.423969	0.648437	-1.653833	0.2160
INSWH	0.002335	0.027922	0.983629	0.1337
BODS	-0.088895	0.126479	-3.702843	0.0102
R-squared	0.072137	Mean dependent var		0.070264
Adjusted R-squared	-0.013776	S.D. dependent var		1.362189
S.E. of regression	1.371540	Akaike info criterion		3.564384
Sum squared resid	101.5805	Schwarz criterion		3.773819
Log likelihood	-100.9315	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.646306
F-statistic	12.39652	Durbin-Watson stat		2.328415
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00000			

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The multiple regression line is as written below:

$$ETR = 4.312063 + 0.534338AUDCSz + 0.627341BODI - 0.423969CEOD + 0.002335INSW - 0.088895BODS + \mu$$

Considering the regression results above, when the independent variables- Audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI), CEO duality (CEOD), institutional ownership (INSWH) and board size (BODS) of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria are held constant (equal Zero), the dependent variable- Effective tax rate increased at a constant average of approximately 4.31%. However, a one percent (1%) rise in audit committee size (AUDCSz), board independence (BODI) and institutional ownership (INSWH) increase effective tax rate by approximately 0.53%, 0.62% and 0.002% respectively while an increase in CEO duality and Board size by one percent (1%) increase effective tax rate by approximately 0.42% and 0.08% respectively.

4.3.1 Hypothesis one

H₀: Audit committee size has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Audit committee size has significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria caused by audit committee size (AUDCSz) is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.4469 given at $T_{0.05,6}$. From the result in table 4.5 above, the Tcal of 3.551896 is greater than Ttab given at $T_{0.05,6}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that audit committee size has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternate hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,6}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0165) is less than 0.05.

4.3.2 Hypothesis two

H₀: Board independence has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Board independence has significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

From the result in table 4.5 above, the Tcal of 4.174241 is greater than Ttab given at $T_{0.05,6}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that Board independence has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternate hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,6}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0023) is less than 0.05.

4.3.3 Hypothesis three

Ho: CEO duality has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

H₁: CEO duality has significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

From the result in table 4.5 above, the Tcal of 1.653833 is less than Ttab given at $T_{0.05,6}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that CEO duality has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternate hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $T_{0.05,6}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.2160) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.4 Hypothesis four

Ho: There is no significant relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

H₁: There is significant relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

From the result in table 4.5 above, the Tcal of 0.983629 is less than Ttab given at $T_{0.05,6}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternate hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $T_{0.05,6}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.1337) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.5 Hypothesis five

Ho: Board size has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Board size has significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

From the result in table 4.5 above, the Tcal of 4.174241 is greater than Ttab given at $T_{0.05,6}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that size has no significant relationship with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternate hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,6}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0023) is less than 0.05.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.4.1 Audit committee size and effective tax rate

The finding that audit committee size has a significant positive relationship with effective tax rate suggests that larger audit committees are effective in reducing tax avoidance practices among listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. This is consistent with the notion that audit committees play a crucial role in overseeing financial reporting and ensuring compliance with tax laws and regulations. A larger audit committee may bring more diverse expertise and experience, enabling more effective monitoring and oversight of tax practices. This, in turn, can lead to a reduction in tax sheltering strategies, as evidenced by the positive relationship with effective tax rate. This is in line with the findings of Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021) and that of Uniamikogbo, Bennee and Adeusi (2019). These studies established that the size of board moves in the same direction with tax aggressiveness.

4.4.2 Board independence and effective tax rate

The significant positive relationship between board independence and effective tax rate indicates that boards with a higher proportion of independent directors are more effective in reducing tax avoidance practices among listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Independent directors are often seen as more objective and less influenced by management, which can enable them to make more informed decisions that prioritize tax compliance over tax avoidance. This finding suggests that board independence is an important corporate governance mechanism that can help mitigate tax sheltering strategies. This is in agreement with the findings of Ogbodo and Abusomwan (2021). The estimation results revealed that board independence have a negative coefficient and significant at 5% suggesting that an increase in these board structure variables results in a reduction in the tax paid/ pre-tax income ratio and this implies an increase in tax sheltering practices.

4.4.3 CEO duality and effective tax rate

The non-significant negative relationship between CEO duality and effective tax rate suggests that CEO duality does not have a significant impact on tax sheltering strategies among listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. CEO duality occurs when the CEO also serves as the chairman of the board, which can potentially lead to a concentration of power and a lack of effective oversight. However, the findings of this study do not provide evidence to support the notion that CEO duality leads to increased tax avoidance practices. This is both in consonance and deviance with the findings of Ezejiofor and Ezenwafor (2020) which revealed that CEO duality is significant and has a positive coefficient on tax planning of food and beverage companies in Nigeria indicating the possibility of tax avoidance practices.

4.4.4 Institutional ownership and effective tax rate

The non-significant positive relationship between institutional ownership and effective tax rate suggests that institutional ownership does not have a significant impact on tax sheltering strategies among listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Institutional ownership can potentially play a monitoring role, ensuring that firms comply with tax laws and regulations. However, the findings of this study do not provide evidence to support the notion that institutional ownership is effective in reducing tax avoidance practices. The finding that institutional ownership has a non-significant positive relationship with effective tax rate partially aligns with Sarhan (2023), who found that institutional shareholding weakens the positive relationship between CSR and tax citizenship. However, the non-significant relationship in the current study suggests that institutional ownership may not play a crucial role in tax avoidance practices, which contrasts with some prior research.

4.4.5 Board size and effective tax rate

The finding that board size has a non-significant negative relationship with effective tax rate, but with a significant p-value of 0.0102, suggests that larger boards may be associated with increased tax avoidance practices among listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Although the relationship is not significant at the conventional 5% level, the p-value is close to being significant, and the coefficient is negative, indicating that larger boards may lead to less effective oversight and monitoring of tax practices. This finding is consistent with the notion that larger boards can be more difficult to manage and may lead to communication and coordination challenges, potentially resulting in less effective governance. The finding that board size has a non-significant negative relationship with effective tax rate aligns with Ali and Zoghlami (2023), who found no significant effect of board size on tax avoidance. Similarly, Sani and Umar (2023) found a weak and insignificant correlation between board size and tax evasion. These studies suggest that board size may not be a significant determinant of tax avoidance practices.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of findings

This present study examined the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The study covered ten (10) year period (2014-2023) with particular emphasis on audit committee size, Board independence, CEO duality institutional ownership and Board size. Effective tax rate applicable to these selected firms served as a surrogate for tax sheltering strategies. Below is a summary of findings gathered through a panel multiple regression analysis.

1. Audit committee size has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.5343{0.0165}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. This signifies a reduction in tax avoidance practices.
2. Board independence has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.62734{0.0023}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. This signifies a reduction in tax avoidance practices.
3. CEO duality has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.4239{0.2160}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.
4. Institutional ownership has a non-significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.0023{0.1337}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

5. Board size has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.0088{0.0102}) with effective tax rate of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable insights into the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The findings suggest that audit committee size and board independence are effective in reducing tax avoidance practices, as evidenced by their significant positive relationships with effective tax rate. These results highlight the importance of robust corporate governance mechanisms in promoting tax compliance and reducing aggressive tax planning behaviors. The study's findings have implications for policymakers, regulators, and corporate governance practitioners in Nigeria. The results suggest that strengthening audit committees and promoting board independence can be effective strategies for reducing tax avoidance practices among listed conglomerate firms. However, the non-significant relationships between CEO duality, institutional ownership, and board size with effective tax rate highlight the complexity of the relationships between corporate governance mechanisms and tax sheltering strategies.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been put forward.

1. Regulators and policymakers should consider implementing measures to strengthen audit committees, such as increasing their size, expertise, and independence, to enhance their ability to oversee tax compliance and reduce tax avoidance practices.
2. Listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria should prioritize board independence by ensuring that a significant proportion of board members are independent directors, which can help reduce tax avoidance practices and promote tax compliance.
3. Although CEO duality was not significant in this study, firms and regulators should continue to monitor its impact on tax avoidance practices and consider implementing measures to mitigate potential risks, such as separating the roles of CEO and Chairman.
4. Firms and regulators could explore ways to leverage institutional ownership to promote tax compliance, such as encouraging institutional investors to actively engage with firms on tax governance and compliance issues.
5. Firms should consider optimizing their board size to ensure effective governance and decision-making, potentially reducing the risk of tax avoidance practices. This could involve regularly reviewing board composition and size to ensure it is aligned with the firm's needs and objectives.

5.4 Suggestions for further studies

Other studies should consider the following aspects.

1. Investigate the impact of other corporate governance mechanisms, such as audit quality, board diversity, or executive compensation, on tax avoidance practices in Nigeria.
2. Focus on specific industries, such as banking or manufacturing, to determine whether the relationships between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance practices vary across industries.
3. A comparative study could be conducted to examine the differences in corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance practices between listed and non-listed firms in Nigeria.
4. Investigate the impact of regulatory environment on the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance practices in Nigeria.
5. A longitudinal study could be conducted to examine the trends and changes in corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance practices over a longer period.

5.5 Contributions to knowledge

1. The study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between corporate monitoring mechanisms and tax avoidance practices in Nigeria, contributing to the existing body of knowledge on corporate governance and tax compliance.
2. The findings highlight the importance of audit committee size and board independence in reducing tax avoidance practices, providing insights for policymakers and regulators on effective corporate governance mechanisms.

3. The study contributes to a deeper understanding of tax avoidance practices in the Nigerian context, highlighting the need for context-specific research and policies to address tax compliance issues.

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